

Research Article

Knowledge, Perception, and Attitude of Undergraduate Medical Students towards the Hermaphrodites

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- Intersex
- Attitude
- Perception
- Stigma
- Discrimination Health
- Fundamental rights
- Knowledge

Abstract

Although hermaphroditism is a well-known phenomenon, this population remains deprived of their fundamental rights and face ridicule and discrimination in almost all walks of life. The structural, interpersonal and individual stigma they face leads to stress, anxiety, and depression among other health conditions. The aim was to gauge the perceptions of and attitudes towards hermaphrodites amongst the medical students. We conducted a cross-sectional survey in Allama Iqbal Medical College Lahore (AIMC), Pakistan. The study lasted for one month and three days (24th April-27th May, 2017). We conducted a non-probability purposive sampling survey on 300 Bachelor of Medicine, Bachelor of Surgery (MBBS) students of AIMC, choosing 60 students from each year via convenient sampling. We entered the data into SPSS version 17.0 and analyzed the data through the same program. It was found that 83.7% of the participants were fully aware of the term 'Hermaphrodite' and a large percentage (93.7%) expressed that the work needed to be done for their welfare. When asked whether they would be comfortable while working with them as colleagues, 45.3% responded in affirmative. However, only 18% of the respondents responded that they had actually worked for the welfare of the hermaphrodites. Through our research, we aimed to detect the willingness to work for hermaphrodite welfare in the population to which majority of the study population answered in affirmative but admitted to never having actually worked on any welfare projects. The results also show that people do believe hermaphrodites are vulnerable to sexual assault and agreed that they are deprived of their rights in the basic fields like health care and education.

ABBREVIATIONS

MBBS: Bachelor of Medicine, Bachelor of Surgery; AIMC: Allama Iqbal Medical College; DSD: Disorder of Sexual Development; NIC: National Identity Cards; DPT: Doctor of Physical Therapy; MLT: Medical Laboratory Technician

INTRODUCTION

A genetic condition in which the affected person has mature gonadal tissue of both types (ovarian and testicular) is termed as true hermaphroditism [1]. The word hermaphrodite denotes ambiguous genitalia; however, it is now considered misrepresentative and so has been replaced by the term intersex. The estimated prevalence is approximately 1/20,000 births. An autosomal pattern of inheritance proposes that genes determining sexual maturity are not restricted to the sex chromosomes [2].

We define stigma as the societal practice of tagging, stereotyping, and denying human difference as a method of social authority [3].

Hermaphrodites face structural, interpersonal and individual stigma including hate crimes, sex crimes, infanticides, poverty, employment discrimination and neglect, which is associated with negative health outcomes such as depression, anxiety, suicidality, substance abuse, and HIV exposure [3].

Stigma and prejudice add on to the prevalent stress resulting in proximal (internalized anxiety) and distal (experiences of rejection) processes as described by Meyer [4].

In a US study of 402 hermaphrodites, 56% reported experiencing verbal harassment; 37% faced employment discrimination; and 19%, physical violence [5].

Eastern and European societies vary in their attitude towards

rearing of children with DSD (a disorder of sexual development) and parental partiality for male gender override the child's sexual potential [6].

In Pakistan, there is a denial of the existence of a third gender and those affected by DSD did not possess National Identity Cards (NIC) until 2013. Considering them a mark of disgrace, the families of such hermaphrodite children hand them over to 'Hijra Communities' resulting in their isolation and social seclusion. They face economic, medical and educational deprivation. Forced into prostitution, they are subjected to physical, mental and sexual abuse [7]. According to the 'A report of the national transgender discrimination survey', hermaphrodites face social injustice on various platforms such as in education. On the professional front, they encounter double the rate of unemployment. 90% were confronted with maltreatment and 47% were denied a promotion, which results in the concealment of their true sexual identity. 19% of the hermaphrodites in the survey reported homelessness and 22 % experienced violence at the hands of law enforcing agencies such as the police [8].

In addition to facing discrimination in many public places, hermaphrodites are deprived of basic human dignity in an extremely private area; the restroom. Many plan their routine activities to enable access to restrooms available to them; in preference to being harassed when using gender-specific restrooms [9].

Transgender people of color and with lower incomes face physical and mental health disparities. The cause of increased mental health problems stems from societal pressure, familial rejection, and absence of culturally proficient mental health services [10].

Bioethicists criticize the medical management of DSD in childhood, before the age of consent, except for medical emergencies. Surgical creation of unambiguous genitalia is neither essential nor adequate to ensure the wellbeing of the future adult [11]. The findings of this literature highlight the need for locally based research for higher learning. The sub-themes of this survey will address the following:

1. What do medical students understand by hermaphrodite categories?
2. What are the students' experiences with hermaphrodite people and the emotions these interactions elicit?
3. What do students know about the specific health needs of hermaphrodite people and do they feel competent to address these needs?

We conducted this study to analyze the knowledge, perception and attitude of undergraduate medical students towards hermaphrodites in Pakistan.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study design

Cross-Sectional Survey

Study setting

The study was conducted in Allama Iqbal Medical College (AIMC) Lahore, Pakistan, which is a government institution

affiliated with Jinnah Hospital located on Allama Shabbir Ahmed Usmani Road, Faisal Town, Lahore, Pakistan. The facilities that are present in this institute include hostels, gym, swimming pool, football ground, and cafeteria. Courses offered are Bachelor of Medicine and Bachelor of Surgery (MBBS), Doctor of Physical Medicine (DPT), Medical Laboratory Technician (MLT), and Nursing.

Duration of study

The study lasted for 1 month, 3 days (24th April-27th May, 2017).

Sample size

300 undergraduate medical students of AIMC (first to final year MBBS)

Sampling technique

Non-probability purposive sampling

Sample selection

Inclusion criteria: 300 Medical students of AIMC, first to fifth-year MBBS, during the time period of the study with the first 60 Students available from each of the five years in MBBS

Exclusion criteria: Those medical students who didn't consent to participate including the ones who are non-serious, non-compliant, uncooperative and unwilling to fill the forms

Data collection procedure: This research was conducted on 300 Medical students of MBBS after signing the informed consent. Conveniently 60 students were selected from each of the five study years. Before handing over the self-administered questionnaire, they were assured their anonymity would be maintained and the data would solely be used for research purpose. The Ethics Committee of AIMC gave the ethical consent.

Dependent variables: Knowledge, Perception, and Attitudes of respondents regarding hermaphrodites.

Independent variables: Age, gender, year of study, residential status.

The questionnaire comprised multiple choice questions which aimed to gauge knowledge, attitudes, and perceptions of respondents.

Data analysis procedure

We analyzed our data using the SPSS program version 17.0. Quantitative data mean and + SD was calculated. For quantitative data, frequency and percentages were given. For qualitative data especially the determination of perception and attitude, we analyzed the self-administered questionnaire.

RESULTS

The study was conducted with the students of AIMC, which is attached to Jinnah Hospital, Pakistan. We interviewed 300 MBBS students (60 students from each study year) as shown in Figure 1. 70% (210) females and 30% (90) male students were interviewed in this study. This included 50.67% (152) day scholars and 49.33% (148) boarders. Age of students ranged

from 17 (minimum) to 25 (maximum) years, the mean age is 20.84 with a standard deviation of +/-1.75. For more information on the age of the participants, see Table 1. It was found that 83.7% (251/300) were fully aware of the term 'Hermaphrodite' whereas 14% (42/300) had a vague idea of what the term meant. However, 2.3% (7/300) had no idea what the word hermaphrodite meant (Table 2). 18.7% of students daily encountered a hermaphrodite, 36% saw them weekly, 32.3% monthly whereas 13% had never seen a hermaphrodite in their life (Figure 2). 58.3% of students considered hermaphroditism a medical disorder whereas 10.0% thought of it as a psychological disorder. 31.7% considered it both a medical and psychological disorder.

Moving on to the perception of students towards them, 34.3% felt pity when they first encountered a hermaphrodite. 14% had a feeling of fear, 4.3% had disgust, 43.7% were neutral whereas 1% chose to ridicule and 2.7% were friendly towards them (Table 3). When asked about their perception regarding people pretending to be a hermaphrodite intersex for monetary gains, 59.3% replied

Figure 1 Year of the study of the respondents.

Figure 2 Frequency of seeing a hermaphrodite.

Table 1: Age of respondents.

Age of respondents	Frequency	Percent (%)
17	6	2.0
18	22	7.3
19	47	15.7
20	53	17.7
21	58	19.3
22	58	19.3
23	39	13.0
24	14	4.7
25	3	1.0
Total	300	100.0

Table 2: Knowledge of MBBS students of AIMC about Hermaphrodites.

Variables	Frequency	Percent
Knows about the term hermaphrodite		
Never heard of the word	7	2.3
Had a vague idea.	42	14.0
yes aware of it	251	83.7
Consider hermaphrodite to be a medical disorder	175	58.3
Consider hermaphrodite to be a psychological disorder	30	10.0
Consider hermaphrodite to be a medical and psychological disorder	95	31.7

Table 3: Perceptions of students of AIMC about hermaphrodites.

Variables	Frequency (Out of 300)	Percent
First thought on seeing a hermaphrodite		
Pity	103	34.3
Fear	42	14.0
Disgust	13	4.3
Neutral	131	43.7
Ridicule	3	1.0
Friendly	8	2.7
People pretend to be hermaphrodites to earn money		
Always	20	6.7
Sometimes	178	59.3
Rarely	70	23.3
Never	32	10.7
Considers them more vulnerable to sexual assault		
Yes	236	78.7
No	64	21.3
Perception about issuing NIC to hermaphrodites		
Positive	248	82.7
Negative	17	5.7
Neutral	35	11.7

that it was probable that they pretended sometimes. 23.3% thought that this was rare, 10% believed that this never happens. A small percentage (6.7%) thought that people always pretend to be a hermaphrodite. 78.7% of the respondents consider them to be more vulnerable to sexual assault. The perception regarding including another option for the third gender in the NIC was considered a positive move by 82.7%; negative by 5.7%, and neutral by 11.7% of respondents. Furthermore, only 7.3% of students thought that there is adequate provision of basic health rights for the intersex community in both public and private health sectors whereas a fleeting 68.7 % considered this provision absolutely inadequate. A large percentage (93.7%) expressed that the work needed to be done for their welfare and when asked whether they would be comfortable while working with them as colleagues 45.3% responded in an affirmative.

A set of questions were directed at inquiring about the attitudes of students towards the third gender. 14.3% of students admitted that they had made fun of them on some occasion. 35.7% had never witnessed a situation of verbal or physical abuse towards them whereas 41.3% of students had often witnessed such events, 7.3% witnessed only one such occasion and the remaining 15.7% had rarely seen it. When asked whether they had tried to stop the witnessed abuse, 57% replied that they had chosen not to intervene. Only 18% of the respondents had worked for their welfare, whereas 85.3% people expressed their willingness to work for them if given a chance (Table 4).

Majority of the students (82%) had given them money at some occasion. The reasons for this choice were as follows: pity (16.3%), to get rid of them (12.7%), myths about them (8.7%), and to help them (44.3%). Moreover, 65.7% had a belief that monetary help is justified.

Thus, the majority acknowledges that the third gender is a largely ignored community in the society, not adequately facilitated in basic rights both in the public and private sector.

DISCUSSION

People suffering from hermaphroditism has long been on the receiving end of social stigma in many parts of the world and in Pakistan, the third genders are deprived of all their fundamental human rights including those of health, education, employment, and housing, participation in political and social affairs. They are always looked down upon and are the focus of ridicule and degradation according to the general social consensus. In comparison to "A report of the national transgender discrimination survey" by Grant et al. [8], which was conducted on the third gender in the USA about their harassment experiences, our results also showed that 78.7% of the students believed that the intersex is more vulnerable to sexual assault. According to the transgender, 90% of them faced discrimination and mistreatment at the workplace. One-quarter of them reported that they had lost their jobs on the basis of their gender disparity. A large majority of this community expressed that they often had to make deliberate efforts in order to hide their sex to avoid the maltreatment at their employment place. On the other hand, our research indicates that 45.3% of the students would feel comfortable while working with them as colleagues while only a small minority (10%) said that they would be uncomfortable. There is a significant difference between the two figures which can be attributed to the fact that our research was conducted on a small educated proportion of the society and the results cannot be reliably projected on to the entire community. Also, this question in our research was aimed at judging the knowledge, perception of the students and their attitudes, which can be the reason for the difference. Another difference arises because of the fact that we only included the educated class of the society already knowing somehow about this genetic condition.

A study conducted at the University of Delaware [12] concluded that 65% of Americans were of the belief that intersex should receive protection provided by anti-discrimination laws. Our research that was conducted in Pakistan showed a very optimistic perception of the students as 82.7% considered the initiative of issuing NIC to hermaphrodites in 2013 as a positive step. In support of our research, the study at Delaware [12] showed that 82% of Americans believed that the transgender community deserves the same rights and protections as other American citizens. In contrast to this, the real picture of our part of the world shows that only 7.3% of students consider that there is adequate provision of the basic health rights of hermaphrodites in both public and private sector. This discrepancy of figures is attributed to the fact that the research in America was directed at analyzing the opinions of people regarding the need of provision of health services to hermaphrodites in hospital setups, whereas our research question was aimed at judging the actual percentage of people who have observed that the provision of basic health

Table 4: Attitudes of students towards hermaphrodites.

Comfort whilst working with them as colleagues		
Not at all	20	6.7
Not Sure	114	38.0
Uncomfortable	30	10.0
Comfortable	136	45.3
Total	300	100.0
Made fun of them		
Yes	43	14.3
No	257	85.7
Witnessed a situation of verbal or physical abuse towards them		
Never	107	35.7
Often	124	41.3
Rarely	47	15.7
Once	22	7.3
Tried to stop the witnessed abuse		
never witnessed abuse	107	35.7
Yes	22	7.3
No	171	57
Done something for their welfare		
Yes	54	18.0
No	246	82.0
Willingness to work for the welfare		
Yes	256	85.3
No	44	14.7
Ever given money to them		
Yes	246	82.0
No	54	18.0

services to hermaphrodites is adequate.

A study conducted in the USA by Dr. Redfern on perceptions and attitudes of law personnel [13]; also an educated class, concluded that 95% of respondents were well informed of the term transgender, a minority (3%) did not know what it meant while 2% had never heard of the term. Accordingly, in our survey, 83.7% of the respondents were aware of the term whereas 2.3% had never heard of the term. These percentages show that people are well aware of this term in most parts of the world. Moreover, the same study showed that 37% of respondents considered this condition to be a normal variation in human development while 58% disagreed with it being a mental illness. Furthermore, the result of our study shows that 58.3% believed hermaphroditism a medical illness and 10% thought of it as a psychological disorder.

In a research by Hughto [3], it was established that recent years showed an initiative to be more inclusive of transgender in non-discrimination policies, with many states have passed laws to provide transgender with equal protections. Similarly, our research indicates that 93.7% of the students believe that work needs to be done for their welfare, but only 18% had actually worked for their welfare. Our study has certain limitations; we included only the undergraduate medical students so the results can't be generalized to the whole population. We included very few questions to establish the students' perception and knowledge about the hermaphrodites. We didn't report the basic fields of life hermaphrodites are lacking rights in detail.

CONCLUSION

From our results, we conclude that medical students are well informed of the term hermaphrodite and consider it a medical disorder. Majority of the students believe that hermaphrodites are more vulnerable to assault and are deprived of their fundamental rights in fields of health, education, employment, political affairs. There is a general willingness to work for hermaphrodite welfare which is a positive approach, however, work done in this filed up till now has been minimal.

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REFERENCES

1. Nierkerk WA, Retief AE. The gonads of human true hermaphrodites. *Human Genetics*.1981; 58: 117-122.
2. Lowry RB, Bergsma D. Familial true hermaphroditism. *Genetic forms of hypogonadism*.1975; 1: 105-113.
3. Hughto JMW, Reisner SL, Pachankis JE. Transgender Stigma and Health: A Critical Review of Stigma Determinants, Mechanisms, and Interventions. *Soc Sci Med*. 2015; 147: 222-231.
4. Bockting W, Coleman E, Deutsch MB, Guillamon A, Meyer I, Reisner S, et al. Adult Development and Quality of Life of Transgender and Gender Nonconforming People. *Curr Opin Endocrinol Diabetes Obes*. 2016; 23: 188-197.
5. Bockting WO, Miner MH, Romine RES, Hamilton A, Coleman E. Stigma, Mental Health, and Resilience in an Online Sample of the US Transgender Population. *Am J Public Health*. 2013; 103: 943-951.
6. Ozbey H, Etker S. Disorders of sexual development in a cultural context. *Arab Journal of Urology*. 2013; 11: 33-39.
7. Ali HA. The Largely Ignored Third Gender: Issues Faced by Hermaphrodites in Pakistan. *JPMS*. 2016; 1: 1-2.
8. Grant JM, Mottet LA, Tanis J. Injustice at every turn. A report of the national transgender discrimination survey. 2011; 1: 1-9.
9. Duggins KL. Students attitudes towards the transgender community following restroom reassignment. *OTS masters levels projects and papers*. 2015; 426: 1-45.
10. Seelman KL, Hernandez LR, Young SR, Tesene M, Kattari L. A comparison of health disparities among transgender adults in Colorado (USA) by race and income. *International Journal of Transgenderism*. 2017; 18: 199-214.
11. Wiesemann C, Ude-Coeller S, Sinnecker GHG, Theyen U. Ethical principles and recommendations for the medical management of differences of sex development/intersex in children and adolescents. *Eur J peadiatr*. 2010; 169: 671-679.
12. Jones PE, Brewer PR, Young DG, Lambe JL, Hoffman LH. Explaining public opinion towards transgender people, rights, and candidates. *American political science association paper*. 2016.
13. Redfern JS. National survey of attitudes of law enforcement personnel towards transgender individuals. *Journal of law enforcement*. 2014; 4.

QUESTIONNAIRE

"Knowledge, Perception, and Attitude of Medical Students towards Hermaphrodites"

Sr. no.: Batch:

Age:

Gender:

Residential status: Boarder/ Day scholar

Year of study a) 1st-year b) 2nd-year c) 3rd-year d) 4th-year e) 5th year

1. Do you know what a hermaphrodite is?

- A. No
- B. I have a vague idea.
- C. Yes

2. Do you consider hermaphroditism a medical disorder?

- A. Yes
- B. No,
- C. Not sure

3. How often do you see a hermaphrodite?

- A. Daily
- B. Weekly
- C. Monthly
- D. Never

4. First thought when you see a hermaphrodite?

- A) Pity) fear C) disgust D) neutral E) ridicule F) friendly

5. Do you think some people pretend to be a hermaphrodite to earn money?
- Always
 - Sometimes
 - Rarely
 - Not Sure
6. Have you ever made fun of a hermaphrodite?
- Yes/ No
7. Have you ever witnessed a situation where a Hermaphrodite was verbally or physically abused?
- Never
 - Often
 - Rarely
 - Once
8. If yes, did you try to stop it?
- Yes/No
9. Do you think hermaphrodites are more vulnerable to sexual assault?
- Yes/No/ not sure
10. Do you think the basic health rights of hermaphrodites are being adequately delivered in public/private sector?
- Yes
 - No
 - Not Sure
11. Do you think work needs to be done for their welfare (regarding basic human rights)?
- Yes/No
12. i) Have you ever done something for their welfare?
- Yes/No
- ii) Are you willing to?
- Yes/No
13. Do you think you will be comfortable working with a hermaphrodite as colleagues?
- Not at all
 - I'm not sure
 - I would be uncomfortable
 - I would be comfortable
14. Do you agree with the initiative of issuing National Identity Cards to Hermaphrodites? A. Yes/no/not sure
15. Have you ever given money to them?
- Yes/No
- If Yes, then why?
- Out of pity
 - To get rid of them
 - False beliefs/myths about them
 - To help them.
16. Do you think it is justified to give them money?
- Yes/No

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